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FIRST RECORD OF *Richelia intracellularis* IN DIATOM-DIAZOTROPH ASSOCIATION WITH *Rhizosolenia spp.* FROM NORTHERN COASTAL WATERS OF SRI LANKA: ECOLOGICAL IMPLICATIONS AND WATER QUALITY ASSESSMENT

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Abstract

Diatom-diazotroph associations (DDAs) are ecologically significant symbioses that enhance new nitrogen inputs in oligotrophic marine ecosystems, yet their presence in Sri Lankan coastal waters has remained unconfirmed. This study is the first morphological record of the heterocystous, nitrogen-fixing cyanobacterium *Richelia intracellularis* as an endosymbiont within two diatom hosts, *Rhizosolenia hebetata* and *Rhizosolenia formosa* from the northern waters of Sri Lanka. Phytoplankton and water quality samples were collected monthly during 2023 from Mathagal, Kankesanthurai, and Akkarai. *Richelia* trichomes (8-14 cells per filament) with terminal heterocysts were observed exclusively at Mathagal (May) and Akkarai (August) within the periplasmic space of host diatoms. Water quality parameters at DDA-positive sites showed nitrate concentrations ranging from 0.05 to 1.43 mgL⁻¹ and phosphate from 0.04 to 0.16 mgL⁻¹. Morphometric characteristics of the Sri Lankan specimens (heterocyst diameter: 9.8–10.6 µm; trichome length: 40-71 µm) align closely with those reported from other Indian Ocean populations. This first record extends the known biogeographical distribution of *Richelia*-diatom symbioses into Sri Lankan waters and highlights their potential contribution to nitrogen cycling in nutrient-limited coastal environments. These findings underscore the need for integrated taxonomic and molecular investigations of DDAs in the northern Indian Ocean.

Keywords: First record, diatom-diazotroph associations, nitrogen fixation, *Richelia intracellularis*, *Rhizosolenia*, Sri Lanka

Introduction

Nitrogen availability often limits primary productivity in marine ecosystems, particularly in tropical oligotrophic waters, where fixed nitrogen sources are scarce (Karl et al., 2002). Biological nitrogen fixation by diazotrophic microorganisms plays a key role in supplying new nitrogen to surface waters, thereby supporting phytoplankton growth and carbon export (Capone et al., 2005). Among marine nitrogen fixers, (DDAs) represent a distinctive and ecologically significant symbiosis. In this relationship, heterocystous cyanobacteria provide fixed nitrogen to their diatom hosts in exchange for organic carbon and physical support (Foster et al., 2011). The filamentous cyanobacterium *Richelia intracellularis* Schmidt is one of the most common endosymbiotic nitrogen-fixers in tropical and subtropical oceans (Janson et al., 1999; Lyimo, 2011). It lives in the periplasmic space between the plasmalemma and siliceous frustule of several diatom genera, mainly *Rhizosolenia*, *Hemiaulus*, and sometimes *Guinardia* and *Chaetoceros* (Villareal, 1992; Gómez et al., 2005). The presence of terminal heterocysts in *Richelia* filaments indicates their potential nitrogen fixation capability (Fay et al., 1965; Venrick, 1974). These symbiotic associations contribute substantially to regional nitrogen budgets (Carpenter et al., 1999; Poulton et al., 2009). Globally, DDAs are estimated to fix approximately 4.79 Tg N annually, accounting for nearly 25% of the total new nitrogen input to the oceans (Carpenter et al., 1999). In the Arabian Sea, nitrogen fixation by *Trichodesmium* and DDAs associations contributes an estimated 15.4 ± 1.5 Tg N per year, representing roughly 92% of the new nitrogen supply to the region (Gandhi et al., 2011). Jabir et al., (2013) observed *Rhizosolenia-Richelia* associations during *Trichodesmium* blooms in the southeastern Arabian Sea, while Padmakumar et al., (2010) documented *Richelia intracellularis* within *Rhizosolenia hebetata* in the northern Arabian Sea during the winter monsoon. Together, these studies highlight the ecological significance of DDAs in nitrogen cycling within the Indian Ocean. Despite extensive records from the Arabian Sea and Bay of Bengal (Iyengar & Desikachary, 1944; Subrahmanyam, 1946; Kulkarni et al., 2010), no confirmed reports of *Richelia*-diatom symbioses exist from the coastal waters of Sri Lanka. The northern coastal region of Sri Lanka, influenced by both Bay of Bengal and Arabian Sea waters through seasonal monsoon circulation, may provide favorable conditions for DDAs to thrive.

This study aimed to investigate phytoplankton diversity in northern coastal waters of Sri Lanka, identify diatom-cyanobacteria symbiotic associations, and document the first occurrence of *Richelia intracellularis* alongside relevant water quality parameters.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This investigation took place over a full year, from January to December 2023, at three locations along the northern coast of Sri Lanka: Mathagal, Kankesanthurai, and Akkarai (Figure 1). Three sampling sites were established at each location, and their precise positions were recorded using a Global Positioning System (Garmin Oregon 750, USA).

At Mathagal, three sites were sampled: Site 1 ($9^{\circ}48'37.98''$ N, $80^{\circ}4'46.05''$ E), Site 2 ($9^{\circ}48'37.98''$ N, $80^{\circ}4'52.53''$ E), and Site 3 ($9^{\circ}48'37.98''$ N, $80^{\circ}4'59.01''$ E). At Kankesanthurai (KKS), the sampled sites were Site 1 ($9^{\circ}49'0.42''$ N, $80^{\circ}2'37.96''$ E), Site 2 ($9^{\circ}49'0.42''$ N, $80^{\circ}2'44.44''$ E), and Site 3 ($9^{\circ}49'0.42''$ N, $80^{\circ}2'50.92''$ E). At Akkarai, the sampled sites were Site 1 ($9^{\circ}49'13.50''$ N, $80^{\circ}7'51.39''$ E), Site 2 ($9^{\circ}49'13.50''$ N, $80^{\circ}7'57.87''$ E), and Site 3 ($9^{\circ}49'13.50''$ N, $80^{\circ}8'4.35''$ E). These sites were selected to represent the northern Sri Lankan coastal environment, characterized by shallow waters and influenced by seasonal monsoons from the Bay of Bengal.

Figure 1. Sampling locations along the northern coast of Sri Lanka showing Mathagal, Kankesanthurai (KKS), and Akkarai

Sampling Strategy

To capture seasonal variations in the phytoplankton community, integrated sampling was conducted monthly. The sampling strategy was designed to simultaneously collect biological material and environmental data, allowing for analysis of diatom occurrence.

Biological Sampling

Plankton samples were collected using a standard conical plankton net with a mouth diameter of 41 cm and a mesh size of 55 μm . Horizontal tows were performed in duplicate, approximately 0.5 meters below the surface, parallel to the shoreline, over a standardized distance of 100 meters. This approach ensured the collection of representative planktonic community samples. Immediately after retrieval, the concentrated plankton was transferred into clean amber glass bottles and preserved with 1% acidified Lugol's solution for subsequent microscopic analysis. All preserved samples were stored in the dark at 4°C to prevent degradation. Live samples were transported to the laboratory in insulated containers for immediate microscopic examination.

Environmental Data Collection

Alongside each plankton tow, environmental parameters such as water temperature (°C), salinity (PSU), pH, and dissolved oxygen (mg/L) were measured *in situ* at a depth of 0.5 m using a calibrated SmarTroll multiparameter handheld device. For each sampling event, pH, salinity, and water temperature were recorded six times, and mean values were calculated. Results are presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Wind speed was measured using a handheld anemometer.

Water Sample Collection and Analysis

Surface water samples were collected in pre-acid-washed 1 L polyethylene bottles at a depth of 0.5 m for laboratory analysis of key biogeochemical variables. Concentrations of dissolved inorganic nutrients, including nitrate (NO_3^-) and phosphate (PO_4^{3-}), were determined using spectrophotometry following standard methods (Grasshoff et al., 1983), with six replicates per analysis.

Phytoplankton Analysis

Preserved samples were concentrated by sedimentation and examined under a trinocular microscope (Euromex iScope: i51153-EPL) at magnifications of $\times 40$, $\times 100$, and $\times 400$. Diatom species and cyanobacterial symbionts were identified using standard taxonomic references (Tomas, 1997; Santhanam et al., 1987). *Richelia intracellularis* was identified based on morphological characteristics such as trichome length, cell number per filament, heterocyst diameter and the position of terminal heterocyst. Cell densities were enumerated using a Sedgewick-Rafter counting chamber and expressed as cells L^{-1} .

Photographs and morphometric measurements of the apical and transapical axes were taken for at least 30 individual specimens using a EuroMex VC-3034 camera attached to the trinocular microscope. Observations were made on a connected computer using Image Focus 4 software at the Advanced Fisheries Science Laboratory, University of Jaffna, Sri Lanka. High-resolution photomicrographs of key diagnostic features were captured for documentation and future reference.

Results

The endosymbiotic cyanobacterium *Richelia intracellularis* was detected exclusively at Mathagal (May) and Akkarai (August), but was not observed at Kankesanthurai. Microscopic analysis confirmed *Richelia intracellularis* as an endosymbiont within *Rhizosolenia hebetata* and *Rhizosolenia formosa* (Figure 2). Trichomes were located within the periplasmic space and consisted of 8–14 vegetative cells with terminal heterocysts. The heterocyst diameter measured $10.2 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{m}$. Each *Rhizosolenia* cell contained 1-4 trichomes (Table 1). The estimated abundance of *Richelia*-containing diatoms ranged from 5 to 30 cells L^{-1} at DDAs-positive stations (Mathagal and Akkarai). Morphometric characteristics of *Richelia intracellularis* are provided in Table 2.

Table 1. Taxonomic hierarchy of *Richelia intracellularis* (Ostenfeld & Schmidt., 1902)

Taxonomic Rank	Classification
Domain	Bacteria
Phylum	Cyanobacteriota (or Cyanobacteria)
Class	Cyanophyceae
Order	Nostocales
Family	Nostocaceae

Taxonomic Rank	Classification
Genus	<i>Richelia</i>
Species	<i>Richelia intracellularis</i>

Figure 2. Photomicrographs of *Richelia intracellularis* endosymbionts within *Rhizosolenia* hosts, A: *Richelia intracellularis* ×400; T: Terminal heterocyst ×400; (a, b) *Rhizosolenia formosa* ×400; (c) *Rhizosolenia formosa* ×100; (d, e) *Rhizosolenia hebetata* ×400.

Table 2. Morphometric characteristics of *Richelia intracellularis*.

Parameter	<i>R. hebetata</i> (Mathagal)	<i>R. formosa</i> (Akkarai)
Trichomes per host cell	1–3	2–4
Cells per trichome	8–13	10–14
Heterocyst diameter (µm)	9.8 ± 1.0	10.6 ± 1.2

Parameter	<i>R. hebetata</i> (Mathagal)	<i>R. formosa</i> (Akkarai)
Trichome/ Filament length (μm)	40–65	48–71
Host cell length (μm)	210–490	180–320
Host cell diameter (μm)	8–29	6–18

Morphometric analysis of the *Rhizosolenia-Richelia* symbiosis showed clear differences between the two host species and their cyanobionts. The heterocysts, which are typically spherical and found at the ends of filaments, showed slight variations in diameter between the two associations. Variations in trichome number, filament length, and heterocyst size matched differences in host cell structure. This suggests possible specific adaptations for each species or different ways of allocating resources within the symbiotic relationship. These changes in morphology could affect nitrogen fixation efficiency and ecological fitness in the coastal waters of northern Sri Lanka.

Previous studies have reported trichome length of 40–71 μm , 8–14 cells per filament, and heterocyst diameter of 9–13 μm (Padmakumar et al., 2010; Jabir et al., 2013). These measurements obtained in the present study fall within these reported ranges, indicating close agreement with existing literature. The occurrence of a terminal heterocyst is also consistent with earlier descriptions.

Water Quality Parameters

The physicochemical parameters were characteristic of sampling locations of Northern Sri Lanka (Table 3). *Richelia*-containing diatoms occurred under the following conditions: at Mathagal (May), temperature was $30.54 \pm 0.50^\circ\text{C}$, salinity 32.93 ± 0.38 PSU, and nitrate 1.43 ± 0.05 mg L^{-1} ; at Akkarai (August), temperature was $30.86 \pm 0.40^\circ\text{C}$, salinity 35.28 ± 0.39 PSU, and nitrate 0.05 ± 0.00 mg L^{-1} .

Table 3. Physicochemical parameters at sampling locations (May & August 2023).

Parameter	Mathagal (May 2023)	Akkarai (August 2023)
Water temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	30.54 ± 0.50	30.86 ± 0.40
pH	7.85 ± 0.03	8.08 ± 0.04
Salinity (PSU)	32.73 ± 0.38	35.28 ± 0.39
DO (mg L^{-1})	8.03 ± 0.09	8.2 ± 0.09
PO_4^{3-} (mg L^{-1})	0.16 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.00
NO_3^- (mg L^{-1})	1.43 ± 0.05	0.05 ± 0.00

Discussion

This study provides the first confirmed documentation of *Richelia intracellularis* in symbiotic association with marine diatoms from Sri Lankan coastal waters, thereby significantly extending the known distribution of DDAs positive sites in the northern Indian Ocean. Previously, such symbioses have been reported from the Arabian Sea, the Bay of Bengal, and the western Pacific (Iyengar & Desikachary, 1944; Subrahmanyam, 1946; Padmakumar et al., 2010; Gómez et al., 2005), but their presence in Sri Lanka's coastal waters remained speculative. The morphological characteristics of the Sri Lankan specimens—trichomes with 8–14 vegetative cells, terminal heterocysts measuring 9.8–10.6 μm in diameter, and trichome lengths of 40–71 μm , fall well within the ranges reported from the Arabian Sea (Padmakumar et al., 2010; Jabir et al., 2013), suggesting a coherent and widely distributed Indian Ocean population. The occurrence of *Richelia* in two distinct host species, *Rhizosolenia hebetata* and *R. formosa*, further confirms the broad but not indiscriminate host specificity previously documented by Janson et al. (1999).

The presence of terminal heterocysts in all observed *Richelia* filaments is a key diagnostic feature indicative of potential nitrogen-fixing capability (Fay et al., 1965). In oligotrophic tropical waters, where fixed nitrogen often limits primary productivity, such endosymbiotic associations provide a significant competitive advantage by alleviating nitrogen limitation within the host's immediate microenvironment (Villareal, 1992; Foster et al., 2011). Although the numerical abundance of *Richelia*-containing diatoms was modest (estimated $<5\text{--}30$ cells L^{-1}), this is consistent with observations from the southeastern Arabian Sea (Jabir et al., 2013).

The presence of heterocysts indicates potential for nitrogen fixation. However, without direct measurements (e.g., acetylene reduction,¹⁵ N_2 incorporation, or *nifH* expression), the actual nitrogen fixation rates and ecological contribution of these associations in Sri Lankan waters remain unconfirmed. Therefore, claims of potential localized nitrogen enrichment, significant nitrogen input, or revision of regional nitrogen budgets based solely on morphological observations are not supported by the present data.

The occurrence of DDAs coincided with water conditions typical of the Southwest monsoon transition period (May and August), including surface water temperatures of 30.5–30.9°C and salinities of 32.7–35.3 PSU. These conditions align closely with those documented for *Richelia*-diatom associations elsewhere in the tropical Indian Ocean (Padmakumar et al., 2010; Jabir et al., 2013). Interestingly, detectable nitrate concentrations (0.05–1.43 mg L^{-1}) and phosphate levels (0.04–0.16 mg L^{-1}) were observed at DDA-positive sites, which may reflect either localized nitrogen fixation or background nutrient availability. The absence of *Richelia* from Kankesanthurai, despite similar temperature and salinity ranges, suggests a patchy spatial distribution possibly influenced by local hydrodynamics, nutrient regimes, or competitive interactions, a pattern consistent with reports from the Arabian Sea (Jabir et al., 2013) and the western Pacific (Gómez et al., 2005).

This discovery carries significant implications for understanding local marine productivity and nutrient cycling in Sri Lankan waters. While *Trichodesmium* blooms have been previously documented in the region (De Silva, 2020), the role of DDAs in new nitrogen inputs has been entirely overlooked. Given that DDA-associated nitrogen fixation can account for up to 25% of new nitrogen input in some oceanic regions (Carpenter et al., 1999), the presence of *Richelia*-containing diatoms in northern Sri Lankan coastal waters suggests that assessments of estimates of nitrogen budgets for this region may be warranted. Furthermore, these findings highlight the urgent need for expanded phytoplankton monitoring programs that specifically target

diazotrophs, coupled with molecular approaches (e.g., *nifH* gene sequencing) to better characterize the diversity, activity, and biogeochemical significance of diazotrophs in Sri Lankan waters (Zehr & Capone, 2020).

Conclusion

This study presents the first confirmed record of the heterocystous cyanobacterium *Richelia intracellularis* in symbiotic association with the diatoms *Rhizosolenia hebetata* and *Rhizosolenia formosa* from the coastal waters of northern Sri Lanka. The association was seasonal and spatially patchy, observed in May at Mathagal and in August at Akkarai, but absent from Kankesanthurai. Morphological characteristics of the Sri Lankan specimens, including trichome length (40–71 µm), cell number per filament (8–14), and heterocyst diameter (9.8–10.6 µm), are consistent with those of previously described Indian Ocean populations, suggesting a coherent regional biogeographical distribution. The presence of terminal heterocysts indicates potential nitrogen-fixing capability, and the association occurred under environmental conditions (temperature 30–31°C, salinity 32–36 PSU) comparable to those supporting DDAs elsewhere in the tropical Indian Ocean.

The discovery of *Richelia*-containing diatom symbioses in Sri Lankan waters suggests possible contributions to new nitrogen inputs in otherwise nutrient-limited coastal environments, but direct measurements are required to confirm activity. This finding underscores the necessity for: (1) systematic, year-round phytoplankton monitoring programs targeting diazotrophs across Sri Lankan coastal waters; (2) molecular characterization of *Richelia* strains and their diatom hosts to resolve phylogenetic relationships; and (3) direct quantitative assessments of nitrogen fixation rates (e.g., acetylene reduction, ¹⁵N₂ enrichment, or *nifH* expression) associated with DDAs-positive sites to determine whether regional nitrogen budgets require refinement. Given the potential sensitivity of diazotrophs to ocean warming and nutrient perturbations, future research should also investigate how changing environmental conditions may influence the distribution and ecological function of *Richelia* - containing diatom associations in the northern Indian Ocean.

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Informed consent

“Not available”.

Data availability statement

The data presented in this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest for publishing this study.

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Contribution of authors

Krishnamoorthy Sivagini: Responsible for data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology development, validation, and preparation of the original draft.

Nahmagal Krishnapillai: Contributed to investigation, supervision, validation, and reviewing and editing the manuscript.

Sivashanthini Kuganathan: Led conceptualization, secured funding, contributed to investigation and methodology, managed project administration, provided supervision, handled visualization, and was involved in reviewing and editing the manuscript.

References

- Capone, D. G., Burns, J. A., Montoya, J. P., Subramaniam, A., Mahaffey, C., Gunderson, T., Michaels, A. F., & Carpenter, E. J. (2005). Nitrogen fixation by *Trichodesmium* spp.: An important source of new nitrogen to the tropical and subtropical North Atlantic Ocean. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles*, 19(2), GB2024. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2004GB002331>
- Carpenter, E. J., Montoya, J. P., Burns, J., Mulholland, M. R., Subramaniam, A., & Capone, D. G. (1999). Extensive bloom of a N₂-fixing diatom/cyanobacterial association in the tropical Atlantic Ocean. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 185, 273–283. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps185273>
- De Silva, M. P. (2020). Coastal water quality and pollution in Sri Lanka: A review. *Journal of Coastal Zone Management*, 23(2), 468.
- Fay, P., Stewart, W. D. P., Walsby, A. E., & Fogg, G. E. (1965). Is the heterocyst the site of nitrogen fixation in blue-green algae? *Nature*, 220, 810–812. <https://doi.org/10.1038/220810a0>
- Foster, R. A., Kuypers, M. M., Vagner, T., Paerl, R. W., Musat, N., & Zehr, J. P. (2011). Nitrogen fixation and transfer in open ocean diatom-cyanobacterial symbioses. *The ISME Journal*, 5(9), 1484–1493. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ismej.2011.26>
- Gandhi, N., Singh, A., Prakash, S., Ramesh, R., Raman, M., Sheshshayee, M. S., & Shetye, S. (2011). First direct measurements of N₂ fixation during a *Trichodesmium* bloom in the eastern Arabian Sea. *Global Biogeochemical Cycles*, 25(4), GB4014. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010GB003970>
- Gómez, F., Furuya, K., & Takeda, S. (2005). Distribution of the cyanobacterium *Richelia intracellularis* as an epiphyte of the diatom *Chaetoceros compressus* in the western Pacific Ocean. *Journal of Plankton Research*, 27(4), 323–330. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbi007>
- Grasshoff, K., Erhardt, M., & Kremling, K. (Eds.). (1983). *Methods of seawater analysis* (2nd ed.). Chemie.
- Iyengar, M. O. P., & Desikachary, T. V. (1944). A systematic account of some marine Myxophyceae of the South Indian coast. *Journal of Madras University*, 16, 37–68.
- Jabir, T., Dhanya, V., Jesmi, Y., Prabhakaran, M. P., Saravanane, N., Gupta, G. V. M., & Hatha, A. A. M. (2013). Occurrence and distribution of a diatom-diazotrophic cyanobacteria association during a *Trichodesmium* bloom in the southeastern Arabian Sea. *International Journal of Oceanography*, 350594. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/350594>
- Janson, S., Wouters, J., Bergman, B., & Carpenter, E. J. (1999). Host specificity in the *Richelia*-diatom symbiosis revealed by hetR gene sequence analysis. *Environmental Microbiology*, 1(5), 431–438. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1462-2920.1999.00053.x>
- Karl, D., Michaels, A., Bergman, B., Capone, D., Carpenter, E., Letelier, R., Lipschultz, F., Paerl, H., Sigman, D., & Stal, L. (2002). Dinitrogen fixation in the world's oceans. *Biogeochemistry*, 57/58, 47–98. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1015798105851>

- Kulkarni, V. V., Chitari, R. R., Narale, D. D., Patil, J. S., & Anil, A. C. (2010). Occurrence of cyanobacteria-diatom symbiosis in the Bay of Bengal: Implications in biogeochemistry. *Current Science*, 99(6), 736–737.
- Lyimo, T. J. (2011). Distribution and abundance of the cyanobacterium *Richelia intracellularis* in the coastal waters of Tanzania. *Journal of Ecology and the Natural Environment*, 3(3), 85–94.
- Ostenfeld, C. H., & Schmidt, J. (1902). Plankton fra det Røde Hav og Adenbugten [Plankton from the Red Sea and the Gulf of Aden]. *Videnskabelige Meddelelser fra Dansk Naturhistorisk Forening*, 1901, 141–182.
- Padmakumar, K. B., Menon, N. R., & Sanjeevan, V. N. (2010). Occurrence of endosymbiont *Richelia intracellularis* (Cyanophyta) within the diatom *Rhizosolenia hebetata* in Northern Arabian Sea. *Journal of Marine Biological Association of India*, 52(1), 16–21.
- Poulton, A. J., Stinchcombe, M. C., & Quartly, G. D. (2009). High numbers of *Trichodesmium* and diazotrophic diatoms in the southwest Indian Ocean. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 36(15), L15610. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009GL039719>
- Santhanam, R., Ramanathan, N., Venkataramanujam, K., & Jegatheesan, G. (1987). Phytoplankton of the Indian seas. In *Aspects of marine botany*. Daya Publishing House.
- Subrahmanyam, R. (1946). A systematic account of the marine plankton diatoms of the Madras coast. *Proceedings of the Indian Academy of Sciences B*, 24(4), 85–197.
- Tomas, C. R. (1997). *Identifying marine phytoplankton*. Academic Press.
- Thronsen, J., Hasle, G. R., & Tangen, K. (2025). *Microplankton in Norwegian marine waters*. Almatel Forlag.
- Venrick, E. L. (1974). The distribution and significance of *Richelia intracellularis* Schmidt in the North Pacific Central Gyre. *Limnology and Oceanography*, 19(3), 437–445. <https://doi.org/10.4319/lo.1974.19.3.0437>
- Villareal, T. A. (1990). Laboratory culture and preliminary characterization of the nitrogen-fixing *Rhizosolenia–Richelia* symbiosis. *Marine Ecology*, 11(2), 117–132. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0485.1990.tb00233.x>
- Villareal, T. A. (1992). Marine nitrogen-fixing diatom-cyanobacteria symbioses. In E. J. Carpenter, D. G. Capone, & J. G. Rueter (Eds.), *Marine pelagic cyanobacteria: Trichodesmium and other diazotrophs* (pp. 163–175). Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Zehr, J. P., & Capone, D. G. (2020). Changing perspectives in marine nitrogen fixation. *Science*, 368(6492), eaay9514. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aay9514>